

Characterising Mission Implementation Contexts

Deliverable No. 3.1

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Executive Summary

Grand challenges, be they Sustainable Development Goals or Grand Societal Challenges, capture societal needs that are currently unmet and often require international and multisector solutions. During the preparation of the Horizon Europe framework programme, a decision was taken to develop a pragmatic approach to tackling grand challenges with the design of “missions”, visible in the Lamy Report, which proposed a **mission-oriented, impact-focused approach** to address global challenges (Lamy, 2017). Whilst societal challenges may be considered as the broader social problem aim or benefit that is being sought (e.g., fighting climate change), missions represent a more narrowly defined set of activities that are supposed to deliver a verifiable result on a planned timescale that can be used to measure progress in overcoming the societal challenge.

In the past year, Horizon Europe has seen the launch of five missions that aim to drive, direct and orchestrate the European research and innovation ecosystem to provide solutions that can transform European society for the better.

The MOSAIC project has decided to align itself with one of the Horizon Europe missions: 100 climate neutral and smart cities by 2030. For MOSAIC to successfully align and embed its co-creation approaches within this mission, it is necessary to understand (a) what is specifically new about “missions” versus previous initiatives, (b) do missions bring new challenges for innovation and (c) are their new requirements that any co-creation activity should take into account?

With these questions in mind this report “Characterising Mission Implementation Contexts” aims to get to grips with the broader notion of societal “Missions” and to report on the nature of the five Horizon Europe missions. The purpose of the report is to provide key background information for MOSAIC Deliverable 3.2 which cross-charts co-creation approaches and needs with the Horizon Europe mission context.

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1. Introduction

Challenges such as climate change, the ageing population and food security are coming to dominate the policy agenda. One example is the articulation of 17 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals which identify global challenges that need to be addressed to preserve a high quality of life and to avoid environmental deterioration. Recently, “Missions” have been touted as one approach to tackle complex societal grand challenges. Missions break grand challenges down into practical steps that can be taken to tackle grand challenges, they have clear and measurable targets and are time-bound.

Missions are not new; they have been around for a long time and the often-mentioned Apollo programme of lunar missions and the Manhattan project are given as examples of early mission-oriented policies (Foray et al. 2012). However, whilst these early missions focused on technical challenges, landing a man on the moon or creating the atom bomb, current challenges are much more complex requiring a complex mix of technical and societal innovations along with behavioural change.

These “New Missions”, what Robinson and Mazzucato (2019) have labelled as Type-2 missions, are an ongoing experiment in mobilising innovation ecosystems and quadruple helix actors to work in concertation and in collaboration to achieve these ambitious and necessary goals.

A key experiment in mobilising the societal mission approach can be seen in the Horizon Europe programme, with its current emphasis on five Mission Areas, and of course, MOSAIC is embedded in one specific Mission Area experiment: the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission Area. So, it is essential, for MOSAIC to gain an understanding of this rapidly evolving situation of missions.

Key questions for MOSAIC are: (a) what is specifically new about “missions” versus previous initiatives, (b) do missions bring new challenges for innovation and (c) are their new requirements that any co-creation activity should take into account?

The objective of this report is to get a good grounding of the origins and current landscape of societal missions, so as to understand the specific nature of this innovation-driving policy approach. The second objective is to capture how the roles that citizens have, or will play, have been framed in the “missions”. The aim is to derive a taxonomy of framings and to observe any gaps in the current discussion around citizen involvement in missions

Therefore, this report acts a background/foundation paper that will be used to help guide the development, implementation and embedding of the MOSAIC co-creation approach. It is also a resource for others outside of the project, that wish to understand the new experiments in “mission-orientation” and what it means for solving societal grand challenges through collaborative research and innovation.

This report is structured as follows. Section 2 takes a broad look at mission-oriented policy, its history and how it has evolved from the original techno-centric Type 1 mission-oriented policies to societal-centric Type 2 missions, detailing the differences and consequences. Section 3 describes, in brief, the Missions of Horizon Europe, summarising the goals and scope of the five missions. Section 3 also zooms into how “citizens” are being framed within the Horizon Europe mission documents – particularly with a view to how the roles of the citizen in contributing to the missions are being described. Section 4 reflects on whether there are new requirements for innovating for missions – with a focus on co-creation in particular.

2. Missions: a “new” hype and hope

2.1 A policy studies perspective on the re-emergence of “Missions”

In the past five years, there have been calls to mobilise mission-oriented policies as a way to address the UN Sustainable Development Goals and other grand societal challenges (Mazzucato 2018, Georghiou et al 2018). Historically, missions were often related to a well-defined outcome, such as putting a man on the moon, which mostly entailed technological challenges. However, modern missions, ranging from the demographic/ageing problem being faced by Western nations to the global challenges concerning climate change, are more complex because there are fewer clear technological challenges and outcomes are less clearly defined (Foray et al. 2012, Robinson and Mazzucato 2019).

In the original “Moon Shot” approach (Mazzucato 2018), mission-oriented policies target the development of *specific* technologies in line with state-defined goals (missions). Mission-oriented policies thus require support from specific sectors, but they are not sectoral policies; they are policies that get many sectors to work together in new ways. Many studies of such techno-centric mission-oriented policies exist, such as analysis of different technology policy initiatives in the US and in Europe (Mowery et al. 2010); and studies of mission-oriented agencies and policy programmes, including military research and development (R&D) programmes, the National Institutes of Health (Sampat 2012), grand missions of agricultural innovation in the US (Wright 2012), and in energy (Anadon 2012), among others.

Such mission-oriented investments have increasingly been found to be important for allowing innovation to take off in a way that generates long-term growth and understanding the history of mission-oriented policies has been crucial for thinking around new policies needed to address grand societal challenges. This is why there is such excitement about the policy approach of missions. However, for these examples of techno-centric missions, such as the Manhattan and Apollo programmes, all funding has been provided solely by nation or federal states. As Foray stated a decade ago, “for current societal challenges, publicly funded R&D, although vital, will be only one of a number of sources of R&D investment” (Foray et al., 2012, p.1698).

Today, directly mobilising missions as an approach to tackled Sustainable Development Goals or other grand challenges is problematic. Missions require long-term commitment to the development of many technological solutions and “a continuing high rate of technical change *and* a set of institutional changes” (Freeman, 1996, p.34). However, grand societal challenges also concern the socio-economic system as a whole, which often implies large-scale transformations with multiple actors and elements (Kuhlmann and Rip 2015, Geels 2004). This is in stark contrast to the techno-centric missions of the past.

Robinson and Mazzucato have labelled the new context and form of mission policies as *Type-2 mission-oriented innovation policies* (Robinson and Mazzucato 2019). Here, policies are not administered by a centralized decision-making authority in a top-down way (Type-1); they are still administered by public agencies, but where these agencies are engaged in decentralized and dynamic innovation ecosystems that include bottom-up innovation, co-creation and variation beyond the direct control of central administrations. Understanding the role of new actors required to address missions that are socio-economic and not just technical, requires Type-2 policies with an “innovation ecosystems” viewpoint. These challenges also require changes at the societal/national systems level (see table 1).

Table 1: Differences in characteristics of old and new mission-oriented policies

Type-1 (Old) Mission-Oriented Innovation Policy <i>Examples include defence and nuclear</i>	Type-2 (New) Mission-Oriented Innovation Policy <i>Examples include environmental technologies and societal challenges</i>
Clear challenges with well-defined goals and specific objectives	Broad challenges with a complex mix of goals and objectives
Single source financing administered by a centralized authority	Multiple sources of financing stemming from a variety of innovation system actors
Centralized control within a government administration in clearly defined value chains.	Decentralized control with a large number of agents involved across many value chains and innovation ecosystems
The goals and the direction of technological development are defined in advance by a small group of experts.	The direction of technical change is influenced by a wide range of actors, including government, private firms and citizens.
Participation is limited to a small group of firms due to the emphasis on a small number of radical technologies.	Emphasis on the development of both radical and incremental innovations in order to permit a large number of firms to participate.
Diffusion of the results outside of the core of participants is of minor importance or actively discouraged.	Diffusion of the results is a central goal and is actively encouraged.
The mission is defined in terms of the number of technical achievements, with little regard to their economic feasibility.	The mission is defined in terms of economically feasible technical solutions to particular societal problems.
Self-contained projects with little need for complementary policies and scant attention paid to coherence.	Complementary policies vital for success and close attention paid to coherence with other goals.

Source: Adapted from Robinson and Mazzucato (2019), which in turn is inspired by Soete and Arundel (1993, p.51).

In a similar vein, Kuittinen et al. 2018 distinguish “accelerator missions”, focusing on driving rapid technological solution development, and “transformer missions” which target larger societal challenges requiring the transformation of socio-technical systems and behavioural change.

2.2 From mission policy to mission action

Whilst there has been great interest at the policy level, there is also increasing activity focusing on mission *implementation*. These have taken different forms and focus on driving research, innovation and the search for solutions, in different ways.

For example, in 2019 the city of Valencia (Spain) made a commitment to improve the quality of life of its citizens whilst also addressing Sustainable Development Goals. Identifying six missions, “Missions València 2030”. Of particular note, is the engaged approach in the identification of the six missions. Between April and September 2019, the City of Valencia engaged with different helices of the quintuple helix (private sector, public sector, universities, civil society and media) to identify four key areas of focus for the city: (1) the Healthy City, (2) the Shared City, (3) the Entrepreneurial City, and (4) the Sustainable City.¹

Figure 1: The process of defining missions in Missions Valencia 2030. Note that direct stakeholder involvement took place in steps 3, 5 and 8.

Another example is the River Clyde Mission in Scotland. Including Glasgow, the river Clyde has approximately 200000 people living within 500 metres of the riverbank. Observing that climate change endangers the livelihoods of those working and living along the river Clyde, and also observing that large swathes of the banks of the Clyde are derelict or unused, a Mission was articulated to ‘Make the Clyde an engine of sustainable and inclusive growth for the city, the region and for Scotland.’ This mission was broken-down into 5 “sub-missions”

1. Create new, good and green jobs and a workforce with the skills to secure those jobs.
2. Use vacant and derelict land for the benefit of the economy, the environment and communities.

¹ More details can be found at www.missionsvalencia.eu.

3. Adapt to climate risks, especially flooding.
4. Accelerate Scotland's progress to net zero.
5. Use the river to create better places for people and communities.

Whilst the Valencia mission involved a lot of citizen engagement and deliberation, the River Clyde Mission, was very much a top-down affair, initiated and coordinated by the Scottish Government's Directorate for Economic Development.²

In France, the mission-oriented programme '*Cultiver et Protéger Autrement* 'Growing and protecting crops differently' Priority Research Programme (PPR), has been designed to contribute to the mission of 'Zero chemical pesticides in agriculture by 2050' and create contributions to solving the societal challenge linked to the sustainability of food security. This mission represents a clear and ambitious objective for society with a specific, and theoretically measurable, direction and timeframe for action. However, the pathways to achieving this mission are uncertain. To meet the ambition for 2050, the PPR programme has financed ten research activities (2 million Euros each) that are thought to be realistic and are potentially breakthrough research projects, representing a clear break from existing solutions. Radical innovations are foreseen to emerge from multiple experiments, based on transdisciplinary, trans-sectoral and multi-actor approaches, tested in secure environments before being generalised for the whole of society.

A note to the reader: These three examples, show the diversity of missions. In the case of Valencia there has been clear citizen involvement in the definition and implementation of the mission. In the Scottish and French cases, missions have originated from Ministry actions. So, it is important to note, that, whilst Missions à la Mazzucato 2019 announce the need for citizen involvement in the design, implementation and evaluation of Missions, it is not automatically the case – the roles that citizens play, and the degree in which they are involved, varies from Mission to Mission.

2.3 Mission history in European Commission

The need for European research to address major societal challenges is mentioned in the Green Paper on the European Research Area adopted by the Commission in April 2007 (Commission of the European Communities, 2007).³ The 2009 Lund Declaration called on European research to focus on "Grand challenges" (in areas such as global warming, tightening supplies of energy, water and food, the ageing society, public health, pandemics and security) instead of the traditional thematic approach that were previously prevalent. The European H2020 research framework programme was built on this premise, with 45% of the budget dedicated to Grand Challenges. During the preparation of the Horizon Europe framework programme, a decision was taken to go one step further in this direction with the design of "missions". The Lamy Report proposed a mission-oriented, impact-focused approach to address global challenges.⁴ Whereas societal challenges may be considered as the broader social problem aim or benefit that is being sought (e.g., fighting climate change), missions represent a

² More recently, a high-level strategy board has been created to coordinate and manage the mission and the five "sub-missions".

³ Commission of the European Communities (2007) GREEN PAPER The European Research Area: New Perspectives COM(2007) 161 final Brussels.

⁴ Lamy, P. (2017) Lab-Fab-App – Investing in the European future we want. Report of the independent High-Level Group on maximizing the impact of EU R&I Programmes.

more narrowly defined set of activities that are supposed to deliver a verifiable result on a planned timescale that can be used to measure progress in overcoming the societal challenge.

During the period 2017 – 2019, Professor Mariana Mazzucato was special advisor to Carlos Moedas, the then Commissioner for Research, Science and Innovation in the European Commission, where she authored two key reports outlining her vision of a mission-oriented approach (Mazzucato, 2018 and 2019). These reports laid the groundwork for what would become the mission-oriented approach taken up in Horizon Europe and captured in the visualisation of figure 2. The expert group "Economic and Societal Impact of Research and innovation (ESIR)", which was created in 2017 to advise Carlos Moedas, also played a key role in the elaboration of the Mission-oriented R&I policy.⁵

Figure 2: The layers and interlinkages between Sustainable Development Goals and Grand Challenges, Missions and what Mariana Mazzucato labelled as “Mission Projects” (Mazzucato 2018).

3. Horizon Europe: Five European Mission Areas

The European Missions have been designed to catalyse and drive large-scale transformations in key areas through ambitious and realistic game-changing solutions, that will provide public goods to Europe’s citizens. To be in line with the definition of societal missions, each mission articulates a clear, measurable and time-bound target, mobilising different stakeholders and actions around a common goal. The legal grounding of the European Missions can be found in the Horizon Europe Regulation, which outlines a set of criteria including that the “common goal” must be linked to an urgent societal challenge and also be relevant to a wide range of stakeholders from all parts of the quadruple helix.

European Missions have the objective of linking various initiatives across different disciplines, mobilise and galvanise policymakers, the private sector, researchers, and civil society, and to take advantage of, or stimulate new, public and private investments towards the “common goal”.

Whilst research and innovation are seen as key in the European Missions, the envisaged major transformations requires major policy and governance changes, along with behavioural changes across

⁵ ESIR (2018) ESIR Memorandum II: implementing EU missions. EC DG R&I.

society. To support the creation of the European missions, the European Commission set up five Mission Boards of approximately 15 experts representing various corners of the quadruple helix. Each board is supported by a broader “Assembly” involving a large number of experts to offer ideas and insights to the Mission Boards.

Five Mission Areas were set up and have led to the definition of five missions, each with a clearly articulated and ambitious goal, which is time-bound. Below we outline, in brief, the five missions.

3.1 Mission Starfish 2030: Restore Our Ocean and Waters

It has been increasingly recognised that both climate change and the effects of other human activities is leading to unprecedented pressures on ocean, coastal and inland water networks. Water is a critical resource and poor governance is leading towards catastrophic changes for both the environment and humanity. It is for this reason, that a systemic look at the water cycle and all of its constituent components was chosen as one of the five European Mission Areas.

Figure 3: The key elements of the water cycle (left) and the five elements of the Starfish mission (Right).
(Source: European Commission (2021) Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 - Implementation Plan)

The objective of this Mission is to restore the health of the EU’s Ocean, seas and waters by 2030, and has been designed to deliver on the European Union’s 2030 targets for protecting and restoring ecosystems and biodiversity, for zero pollution, and for the decarbonisation and reduction of net greenhouse gas emissions towards climate-neutrality.

As with all missions by definition, the Starfish Mission has identified a number of clear and measurable targets that, if achieved, can be considered as “mission success” (see Figure 3).

For the Starfish mission, in this report we have used our own labelling to designate the announced Mission “Objectives” as “sub-missions”. The “Objectives” can be considered missions in their own right but are encompassed within the overall Horizon Europe Mission. For the Starfish Mission, we identify 3 “sub-missions”:

*Sub-mission 1*⁶. Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030:

Measurable target 1: Protect a minimum of 30% of the EU's sea area and integrate ecological corridors, as part of a true Trans-European Nature Network.

Measurable target 2: Strictly protect at least 10% of the EU's sea area.

Measurable target 3: Restore at least 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers.

*Measurable target 4*⁷: Contribute to relevant upcoming marine nature restoration targets including degraded seabed habitats and coastal ecosystems.

Sub-mission 2. Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters, in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil:

Measurable target 1: Reduce by at least 50% plastic litter at sea.

Measurable target 2: Reduce by at least 30% microplastics released into the environment.

Measurable target 3: Reduce by at least 50% nutrient losses, the use and risk of chemical pesticides.

Sub-mission 3. Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy:

Measurable target 1: Eliminate greenhouse gas emissions from maritime economic activities in the EU and sequester those emissions that cannot be avoided (net zero maritime emissions).

*Measurable target 2*⁸: Develop zero-carbon and low-impact aquaculture, and promote circular, low-carbon multi-purpose use of marine and water space.

A note to the reader: As can be seen in the footnotes, some targets shown above clearly articulate a measure of success, while others remain rather open-ended. This leaves open what indeed is a mission success. This can be seen as a weakness or as an opportunity, the latter meaning that the “mission target” can still be negotiated, perhaps through engagement and co-creation with the quadruple helix. This point will be explored further in workpackage 6 of the MOSAIC project.

⁶ As critical researchers, we observe that the Starfish sub-missions and associated measurable targets, do not include a fixed time period for delivery. If we would stay true to the definition of “Mission” as defined in sections 1 and 2 of this report, we could say that such targets require the inclusion of a fixed time horizon.

⁷ The envisaged size of the contribution is not clearly articulated to be able to see what is the specific target.

⁸ The degree of development in this target is not clearly articulated, which may cause problems with actually “measuring” this target.

Figure 4: The three “sub-missions” of the Starfish mission.
 (Source: European Commission (2021) Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 - Implementation Plan)

To implement the Starfish mission, an overarching logic has been defined comprising of ‘lighthouses’ for the major European sea and river basins. These are envisioned to be key sites for promoting cooperation across specific sea and river basins in Europe. The lighthouses will be supported by investment in research, innovation and demonstration activities to drive solutions for the mission targets, with a particular eye to scalability and scaling strategies. Another key strategy in the overarching logic of the Starfish Mission, is the mobilisation of the different publics. Emphasising deliberative democracy, the Starfish Mission has announced that it will place an emphasis on social innovation practices, participatory approaches, co-design and co-implementation of solutions.

“The Mission will connect Europe’s citizens and local communities with the ocean, seas and waters, facilitate broad ownership and education and co-design the transitions within the communities that will allow the European Green Deal targets to be reached.”

(p35, European Commission (2021) Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 - Implementation Plan.)

By 2025, the Starfish Mission plans to pilot participatory governance, particularly through an EU-wide network of citizen assemblies, to integrate citizen insights into the “lighthouses”. Whilst there is an announced aim that co-design and co-implementation must have been demonstrated, at the time of writing, there is insufficient detail on the nature of the co-design and co-implementation. A key part of the citizen engagement objectives of the Starfish Mission, is the ERA funded citizen science campaign labelled “Plastic Pirates” and supporting citizen data collection and observation.

The Starfish Mission will be implemented in two phases. The first phase (2022-2025) focuses on development and piloting solutions for the three “sub-missions” outlined above. The lighthouses are key in this phase as sites for collaborating, experimenting and piloting. The second phase focuses on solution deployment, solution diffusion and upscaling (2026-2030). Depending on the type of solution, this involves raising the Technology Readiness Level (TRL’s) of technical solutions, reducing barriers to market entry (such as de-risking market deployment) and the replication and adaption of solutions to different locations and contexts.

Stakeholder and citizen engagement

The Starfish Mission proposes to connect citizens with oceans, seas and waters in order to co-design the Blue Transitions needed to achieve the targets defined in the European Green Deal. Stating the importance of inclusion, the Starfish Mission proposes to create a number of forums and activities to involve and empower a variety of stakeholders towards social (and other forms of) innovation and ocean and waters stewardship.

By 2025 the Starfish Mission has promised to have tried and applied deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices to co-design and co-implement solutions. It also has promised to develop and test participatory governance processes, particularly mobilising citizen assemblies as a means for participatory and deliberative democracy. The Mission also promises by 2025 to have upscaled the Plastic Prates – Go Europe citizen science campaign, to promote data collection and ocean and waters stewardship.

Anticipating potential frictions arising from the difficult trade-offs that will be necessary for a sustainable Blue Transition to achieve the Starfish Mission, for sub-mission 3 (Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy), a Blue Forum is envisaged that will support the resolution of conflicts by bringing together all relevant maritime stakeholders.

3.2 Cancer

Cancer has been diagnosed a major societal challenge, with more than 2.5 million European citizens being diagnosed with cancer each year. Coupled with other trends, such as unhealthy lifestyles, environmental pollution in urban environments and the ageing population, it is predicted that the number of yearly cancer diagnoses will increase.

This projected increase is not only seen as a humanitarian disaster it is also seen as an economic challenge – the increasing costs of cancer on the health care sector will cause great pressures on an already overburdened healthcare system.

To this end, the Cancer Mission has the overall ambition to improve the lives of more than 3 million people by 2030 through multiple means: prevention, therapeutics and support systems for those affected by cancer. It also aims to provide a fairer approach to cancer care through creating and implementing more equal access to cancer solutions. Built around four objectives: (1) understanding, (2) prevention, including screening and early detection, (3) diagnosis and treatment, and (4) quality of life, the mission will address fair access to cancer treatment and support systems, innovations in prevention and therapeutics, and childhood cancer.

The Cancer Mission Board has estimated baseline scenarios of the potential reduction in deaths (based on gender) between the years 2021 and 2030, with and without Mission intervention. Building on current trends and cancer efforts by European Member States, the number of deaths across the EU is expected to decrease by 30% for males and 14% for females. Including the anticipated mission actions, the Cancer Mission has the objective of achieving a 40% decrease for Males and a 20% decrease for females.

The Cancer Mission implementation will be guided by five basic principles:

1. **Ensure equity and access:** to knowledge, research and care between and within countries, regions, and between people of different socio-economic backgrounds, genders, and age groups.
2. **Promote innovation:** social innovation, novel approaches to public procurement such as precommercial procurement, Living-Labs and other methodologies should be systematically pursued to stimulate innovation and out of the box solutions in healthcare and related sectors.
3. **Allow for risk taking:** not all innovative approaches will deliver but we can learn from failure and avoid repeating past mistakes.
4. **Work with “the coalition of the willing”:** Not all Member States and associated countries have to work on all specific objectives, but equally national and regional differences in Europe should be taken into account. A group of Member States may decide to advance on certain intervention areas and implement actions, sharing their experiences and best practices with the other Member States.
5. **Communication and citizen engagement:** An informed and engaged citizen community, including cancer patients and survivors, constitutes a great asset for the successful deployment of this Mission through national mission hubs, which will be created for all missions, as well as through annual events

Stakeholder and citizen engagement

The role of citizens in the Cancer Mission is predominantly as potential cancer patients or those affected by cancer in various ways. Thus, citizen engagement is an element articulated in the Cancer Mission, mobilising citizen dialogues, focus groups and eliciting feedback on proposed initiatives.

The Cancer Mission has identified that the health literacy of European citizens could be improved, particularly around objectives (1) understanding and (2) prevention, including screening and early detection and thus a part of the Cancer Mission aims is to communicate and educate to improve health literacy.

Interesting for the MOSAIC project, is that co-design and co-creation is foreseen in the Cancer Mission. For example, one of the envisaged activities is to:

“... co-design a cancer toolkit with citizens and local communities throughout Europe: The toolkit will focus on (1) understanding, (2) prevention, including screening and early detection, (3) diagnosis and treatment, and (4) quality of life. The process of co-designing a cancer toolkit with citizens and local communities itself will serve cancer awareness raising.”

(p37, European Commission (2021) Cancer: Improving the lives of more than 3 million people by 2030 through prevention, cure and for those affected by cancer including their families, to live longer and better - Implementation Plan.)

3.3 A Soil Deal for Europe

Soil health is considered a key asset for Europe. Healthy soils are necessary for both productive and sustainable agriculture, for storing and purifying water as well as for maintaining biodiversity. However, it is estimated that over the past 150 years, more than half of the global topsoil has been lost. Moreover, in the past 40 years, nearly a third of global cropland has been abandoned due to erosion and degradation. According to an analysis by the Mission Board Soil Health and Food, it was concluded that between 60%-70% of soils in the EU are in a state of poor health (A Soil Deal for Europe – Implementation Plan, 2021).

With soil health as a major European societal challenge, the Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe – 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030.” has been launched.

The mission, aims to achieve the following eight objectives:

1. Reduce land degradation relating to desertification
2. Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks
3. No net soil sealing and increase the reuse of urban soils
4. Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
5. Prevent erosion
6. Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops
7. Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
8. Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

These eight specific objectives are coupled with four operational objectives that are essential to mission success and are transversal to all eight objectives (see Fig 5)

*Figure 5: The eight specific objectives and four operational objectives of the “Soil Health Mission”.
(Source: European Commission (2021) A Soil Deal for Europe 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030 - Implementation Plan)*

To tackle the four operational objectives, the Soil Health Mission has identified four necessary “building blocks”: (1) across-scale, interdisciplinary R&I programme with a strong social science component, (2) living laboratories (LLs) and lighthouses (LHs) to accelerate the creation and uptake, of solutions, (3) a soil monitoring framework at EU level and at the level of Member States and (4) soil literacy, communication and citizen engagement on soil health objectives.

The timeline of the Soil Health Mission is divided into three, overlapping, phases: Phase 1 is the pilot phase to pool existing resources and to develop implementation structures (2021 – 2025), Phase 2 focuses on the expansion of activities and the development and testing of innovations (2025-2030), and Phase 3 focuses on the scaling up of solutions and adaptation to local contexts and needs (2027-2030).

Stakeholder and citizen engagement

A key ambition of the Soil Health Mission is to create “citizen-led soil stewardship”. Based on the idea that every citizen has the potential to play a role in soil stewardship, the mission foresees that sustainable soil health is only possible if the relationship between citizens and soil health is nurtured and reinforced. Without clear guidelines of how to do so, the Soil Health Mission does outline some key ambitions such as (a) sharing of best practices, (b) networking and connecting proactive communities and civil society groups (particularly (environmental conservation groups, urban food initiatives and city greening initiatives), (c) networking existing initiatives and building guidelines and (d) involve citizens in public decision-making on soil-related matters through participatory and deliberative approaches.

A key approach is to develop tools and approaches for citizen science and the detection and monitoring of soil pollution. This includes the aim to improve citizen awareness of soil pollution issues through an EU-wide citizen science soil pollution initiative. To facilitate citizen involvement, the Soil Health Mission has argued that access to soil health monitoring infrastructure is key. To this end, the mission proposes that practical guidance and tools should be developed, including mobile phone applications in all European languages, that can be used to enable the assessment and aggregation of soil health data from citizens.

Living Labs and Living Lighthouses are seen as nucleating spaces for strong stakeholders and citizen involvement in the Soil Health Mission. In addition, the Soil Health Mission proposes to provide incentives to involve stakeholders and citizens in throughout Soil Health research, though it is currently unclear what such incentives could be.

3.4 Adaptation to Climate Change

Even if we stopped greenhouse gas emissions today, it is predicted that climate related impacts will continue for decades. This stark fact, visible in the dramatic changes in weather systems in recent years, along with increase in droughts and forest fires, poses a major challenge for Europe and the world. In this context, a Mission has been designed to build resilience and adaptation strategies to climate change by supporting **at least 150 European regions and communities to become climate resilient by 2030**.

With approximately 1 billion Euros from the Horizon Europe budget, the Mission aims to enhance and drive climate adaptation and resilience efforts of regions through tight engagement with citizens and regional authorities whilst mobilising significant investment from other public and private resources. In this way, the Resilience Mission is seen as a nucleating and catalytic mission. The aim is to increase the understanding of the potential impacts of climate change on European cities and regions and to build up (and share) know-how on how to prepare for, and mitigate, the negative effects of climate change.

The Resilience Mission is built around three consecutive phases. Phase 1 (2021-2023), labelled the “build-up phase”, lays the groundwork for the Mission organisation, its support system and the selection of between 60 and 100 regions that will be integrated into the mission. Phase 2 (2024-2027), labelled the “deployment phase”, will comprise of development of local adaptation strategies, share solutions across the community of regions taking part, and expand the core group of participating regions and communities. Phase 3 (2028-2030), labelled the “consolidation phase”, moves beyond the timeframe of Horizon Europe and focuses on hardwiring the Mission actions into regions going forward – thus building momentum to ensure the legacy of the Resilience Mission.

These phases encompass a number of steps (see Fig 6) which are captured in three specific objectives. Specific objective 1 focuses on preparing and planning for climate resilience. Specific objective 2 focuses on accelerating transformations to climate resilience. Specific objective 3 focuses on demonstrating systemic transformations to climate resilience.

*Fig. 6 Intervention Steps – Step 1 (Objective 1); Steps 2, 3, 4 (Objective 2), Steps 5, 6 (Objective 3)
(Source: European Commission (2021) Adaptation to Climate Change Support at least 150 European regions and communities to become climate resilient by 2030- Implementation Plan)*

Since climate impacts and adaptation capacities vary widely across European regions, the Resilience Mission promotes a “place-based” approach, tailoring solutions to each regional context is essential. Climate adaptation solutions can include ecosystems and nature-based solutions to mitigate the

effects of climate change, land use and food systems, water management systems, protection and adaptation of critical infrastructures, maintaining health and human wellbeing and producing resilient local economic systems. However, many of the above examples are tightly connected and thus a holistic approach is necessary for climate adaptation strategies.

Of note is that the Resilience Mission, individual and systemic behavioural change is seen as paramount, and thus will be a major focus of adaptation solutions.

*The Mission will have a strong focus on **behavioural change**, both on individual as well as on systemic level, to enable regions to take leadership on transformative adaptation. The Mission will support participating regions and communities in better understanding and using potential social tipping points and systemic leverage points to accelerate transformative changes towards climate resilience.*

(p9, European Commission (2021) Adaptation to Climate Change Support at least 150 European regions and communities to become climate resilient by 2030 - Implementation Plan.)

This focus on behavioural change means that a tight engagement and integration of citizens, as well as other parts of the quadruple helix, is necessary for mission success.

Stakeholder and citizen engagement

Whilst concrete activities have not yet been fully defined, a number of clear ambitions have been articulated for the Resilience Mission. For example, citizens assemblies are considered as an essential and integral part of the Mission, for defining the specific contours of the Resilience Mission in the local/city context and to deliberate and select options. Citizen Science tools (such as data collection) has been identified as key, along with co-creation of prototypes as an important way of mobilising citizens in solution development.

The Resilience Mission also sees the creation of so called “High-level Regional Groups” that will network regional authorities to coordinate and network bottom-up initiatives as well as to scale up and scale out resilience solutions. In a similar vein, “Climate Action Hubs” have been proposed to engage citizens and grassroots initiatives and to prove access to basic tools and methods to develop solutions.

3.5 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030

To be able to achieve The European Green Deal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions to 45% of 2020's emissions by 2030, and to reach 0% emissions by 2050, it is key for European cities to transform their energy, mobility and other systems as well as to catalyse behavioural change in their populations. Whilst a number of European cities have already created their own ambitious climate-neutrality plans, it is clear that support for many more cities is necessary to achieve the targets of the European Green Deal.

With this in mind, the "Cities Mission" was chosen to galvanise, catalyse and drive forward European cities to achieve climate neutrality by 2030. The Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities will mobilise all city stakeholders (local authorities, firms, financiers, citizens etc.) to (a) deliver at least 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030 and to (b) mobilise these 100 cities as demonstrators that can be replicated across Europe to achieve the goals of the European Green Deal by 2050.

Mechanisms of reducing greenhouse gases include, reducing the emissions from fossil fuels in the built environment (residential buildings, offices, factories), reducing or removing emissions from transport, reducing electricity consumption in cities (where the electricity is produced from greenhouse gas emitting powerplants), reducing emissions from waste and reducing emissions from industrial processes.

Potential research and innovation actions that could be part of the initiatives financed by the Cities Mission include, but are not limited to: (a) large-scale demonstration projects, (b) new approaches and tools for human-centred urban planning, (c) experimenting with new forms of finance and business models, (d) living labs and local experimentation for exploring and further understanding about alternatives to current urban socio-technical systems (such as energy provision and consumption, mobility, waste management, etc.) and (e) social innovation.

A central component of the Cities Mission is the Climate City Contracts, which each participating city will develop. The Climate City Contracts represent a clear political commitment by the participating cities to achieve carbon neutrality by 2030 and outline a plan to achieve this, including how the plan will be financed.

A key player in the implementation of the Cities Mission, is the NetZeroCities Mission platform. Comprised of 33 partners from 13 countries, and running from October 2021-September 2025, the platform will support the delivery of the Horizon Europe Mission on 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030, providing technical, regulatory, financial and socio-economic expertise and assistance to cities in developing and implementing their CCCs and related investment plans.

The timeline of the Cities Mission can be broken into four phases. The first phase started with an open call for expression of interest, mobilising an online template for cities to express their interest in participating in the mission and to self-assess their preparedness level (Beginner, Experienced or Frontrunner).⁹ Following an invitation based on the expression of interest, the second phase was the "co-creation of the mission application" by candidate cities. The process had to demonstrate the co-creation of the application with citizens, local authorities and other relevant stakeholders. The deadline was 31st January 2022 with April 2022 seeing the announcement of 100 EU cities, and 12 cities from associated countries, being selected for the Cities Mission. Phase 3 is the co-creation of the Climate City Contracts themselves. Each selected city will receive specific support from the

⁹ In terms of participation, the Cities Mission was launched with the idea to include cities that were more developed in their transition towards climate-neutrality and those at early stages in the climate-neutral journey. Thus, a mix of Beginner, Experienced and Frontrunner cities was actively sought.

“Mission Platform”. Climate city contracts should be co-created with citizens and other relevant stakeholders and articulate the strategies to achieve climate neutrality by 2030, describe the barriers to achieving these strategies, provide a clear governance structure and investment plan. The fourth phase is the implementation of the Climate City Contract.

Stakeholder and citizen engagement

As described above, citizen engagement has been hardwired into the mission application by the cities (Phase 2) and in the development of the Climate City Contract (Phase 3). Recognising that citizens have much to contribute to designing and implementing the Cities Mission (ideas, know-how, local knowledge etc.), meaningful engagement with citizens has been given a high priority in the implementation of the Climate City Contract (Phase 4). Citizens in the role of consumers or users are particularly relevant in the replacement or transformation of the systems targeted for greenhouse gas reduction (waste, energy, transport etc.).

Whilst the variety of citizen engagement approaches will be decided within each individual context, the City Mission has identified Living Labs as playing a key role in interfacing citizens with the development and testing of solutions.

3.6 Citizen roles as framed in key Horizon Europe Mission documents

Whilst all QH actors are important, the MOSAIC Co-Creation Definition pays particular attention to the involvement of citizens and civil society as a whole.

Recalling the MOSAIC definition,

“Co-creation as Open Innovation (Co-innovation) is ‘a form of collaborative innovation, which is initiated by one or more members of the Quadruple Helix (a company, citizens or citizen group, research organisation or public agency), and involves contributors or co-creators from the other “helices” but above all from civil society to co-produce tangible outcomes, such as technologies, services or new organisational structures’.”

Citizens are at the heart of the MOSAIC co-creation definition and thus identifying how the five European Mission Areas frame the roles of citizens in achieving the mission’s objectives is important.

While reviewing the various reports on the five European Missions (see section 3), it became clear that the term “co-creation” is rarely used in the official Horizon Europe documents - the term “Citizen Engagement” is used as a loose umbrella term to capture all activities related to inclusion of citizens. Under this umbrella term, we can see that multiple citizen roles are visible, stretching from citizens as co-innovators to citizens as data collectors to citizens as passive receivers of the outcomes of R&D.

In her report on implementing missions (Mazzucato 2019), Mariana Mazzucato, described roles for citizens in the design, implementation and evaluation of missions. To be able to position the MOSAIC co-creation approach(es) within the ongoing Cities Mission, and to be able to decide ourselves whether

we position our co-creation as an element of citizen engagement (and empowerment), it is important to further clarify the different and diverse “framings”¹⁰ of citizen roles in Horizon Europe missions.

What is the state of citizen roles in the current framing of the Missions? Is there an emphasis on a particular form of citizen involvement? Does this resonate with the MOSAIC definition of co-creation? Where can MOSAIC fit in to the current framing? And perhaps, where should MOSAIC be broadening the role of citizens via co-creation in the Cities Mission?

To this end, MOSAIC has built a draft citizen role framework, mobilising a number of taxonomies, consultancy reports and scientific articles.¹¹ This framework, identifies a number of “roles” that citizens may play in the mission. Using the lens of the quadruple helix as representing the major actors involved in research and innovation/solution development, MOSAIC observed that citizens can play roles in each of the four helices. MOSAIC identified 13 roles that citizens can play in the missions, noting that the same citizen or citizen group can play multiple roles. The table below presents the 13 roles, with a short description and some illustrative examples.

¹⁰ “Framings” refers to how citizen’s roles are being described (or framed) by different stakeholders. In this way, framing is used to describe and designate a role to be played by a citizen. By unpicking such framings, we can reveal the biases and perspectives of those constructing Horizon Europe mission reports – which is clearly important because the documents under study are shaping and directing mission design and implementation!

¹¹ The framework for classifying the roles of citizens in quadruple helix mission-oriented action drew on the following studies: Agger et al. 2018, Anttiroiko 2016; Bergval-Kareborn and Stahlbrost 2009, Chilvers and Kearnes 2016, Cornwall and Gaventa 2001; Cornwall and Coelho 2007, Mayers et al. 2007; Nambisan and Nambisan 2013, Podda et al. 2018, Renting et al. 2012, Sormani et al. 2020, Veeckman ad Van der Graaf 2015, Von Hippel 2006.

Broad roles	Taxonomy of sub-roles	Description	Examples
Citizens as scientists	Data gatherer	Citizens capture and organise data through direct observation.	D-NOSES and odour monitoring in cities. Contributors in citizen science
	Interpreters and thinkers	Citizens synthesise and interpret data, from a variety of sources,	We Count, Cardiff citizens gathered and interpreted data (and its interpretation, to communicate issues to local authorities. https://we-count.net/news/cardiff-citizens-use-data-from-wecount-to-communicate-road-safety-concerns-to-local-councillors
	Problem setter and researcher	Citizens can take a lead role in defining and executing research, often, starting from a problem they encounter in their daily lives. Such activities can be done individually, in collectives and/or in collaboration with other actors.	La Paillasse, totally independent citizen led research Lead amateurs in citizen science make use of fablabs and citizen science spaces, such as La Paillasse in the Gare du Nord region of Paris. https://lapaillasse.org/
Citizens as innovators	Tester	Citizens participate in the trialling and testing of new products, services and solutions, to better develop and hone innovations-in-the-making.	Beta testers for example in Living lab, for example the Smart Mobility Livign Lab. https://smartmobility.london/ . Another example is FAIRCHAIN, trialling Technological and social solutions for FAIRer dairy, fruit and vegetable value CHAINS
	Ideator and Designer	Citizens provide novel ideas and participate in design and co-design activities that can feed into the development of new products, services and practices.	Grenoble CivicLab (GCV) is an open challenge whose participants co-design and prototype projects which include a digital dimension and are of general interest for the citizens of the French region of Grenoble.
	Maker and Developer	Citizens produce their own products and further develop.	Users, makers, hackers and so on in Makerspaces, fablabs, etc. communities
	Diffuser and promoter	Citizens directly catalyse and drive the adoption and diffusion of innovations, particularly among specific user groups. They can act as educators, facilitating the generalisation and embedding of innovations.	The Open food facts platform was facilitated and promoted by citizens. .
Citizens as governors	Budget allocator	Citizens directly shape the targeting of spending, both actively by defining options for spending, and passively by choosing between options.	Participatory budgeting in Paris involves gathering ideas from citizens and then more broadly for citizens to select from those projects which should get financed. https://www.paris.fr/pages/budget-participatif-2021-comment-ca-marche-16525
	Policy definer	Citizens can be engaged in defining agenda for public action.	In France the NGO Agir tous pour la dignité (ATD) Quart monde successfully lobbied for the participation of “poor people” (concerned citizen) to governing agencies for inclusion in local policy definition.
	Jury member	Citizens can participate directly in decision making, evaluating and assessing innovations and their related impacts.	Citizen Assemblies. Citizen Juries, etc. etc.
Citizen as user and consumer	Individual consumer or user	Citizens can shape markets for innovations by selecting between options (when there are choices available).	Selecting between electric car or fossil-fuelled car, or public transport versus private transport.
	Critical user or consumer groups	Citizen as a member of a specific user group or consumer group.	Patient associations, local community collectives.
	Prosumers	Citizens play a hybrid role of both producing and consuming.	Digital online content and Urban agriculture initiatives.

mosaic

Using this framework as a lens to look at the Horizon Europe Mission reports, we observed that many of the roles were articulated as potential means of integrating citizens into the Horizon Europe Missions (See table below).

Broad roles	Taxonomy of sub-roles	Examples from Cities and Resilience missions
Citizens as scientists	Data gatherer	<p>Adaptation to Climate Change Implementation Plan (p15): Citizens will be engaged to co-produce data and knowledge through citizen science and citizen observatories</p> <p>Cities Mission EoI Info Toolkit (p56): The Province of Utrecht "Snifferbike", in which a number of volunteer citizens equip their bicycles with sensors to monitor air quality.</p> <p>Starfish 2030 (p28): Checkpoints for 2025: "20 percent of data collection comes from citizen's science initiatives"</p>
	Interpreters and thinkers	
	Problem setter and researcher	<p>Soil Heal Mission Implementation Plan (p40): ...greater incentives to involve stakeholders and citizens in research throughout, and especially in relation to identifying research needs and delivering research activities.</p>
Citizens as innovators	Tester	<p>Cities Mission EoI Info Toolkit (p3): Living labs for sustainable mobility</p> <p>Cities Mission EoI Info Toolkit (p62): Antwerp Circular South. From 2018 to 2021, the city and its residents tested advanced technological solutions together, through online and offline activities, to collectively reduce resource-consumption, using 'behavioural nudging'.</p>
	Ideator and Designer	<p>Cities Mission EoI Info Toolkit (p18): Co-designing strategies to operationalise implementation can also increase benefits for urban inhabitants.</p> <p>Adaptation to Climate Change Implementation Plan (p15): "the co-design of digital climate services and innovative solutions"</p>
	Maker and (co) developer	<p>Cities Mission EoI Info Toolkit (p55): FinEst Digital Twin, a smart cities collaboration between Finland and Estonia is developing a simulation tool that will allow citizens to shape development of green urban spaces using gaming technology. (Finest Twins, Tallinn-Helsinki dynamic green information model).</p>
	Diffuser and promoter	

Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

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Citizen as governors	Budget allocator	Cities Mission Eol Info Toolkit (p64): Investing in the city – Participatory budgeting (PB) is a collaborative approach to distributed resource allocation and investment, via structures that are co-produced within the political, social and economic environment of each city. Since 1989, when it was first adopted in Porto Alegre (Brazil), PB has spread to over 7000 municipalities worldwide
	Policy definer	<p>Cities Mission Eol Info Toolkit (p72): Inclusive planning processes, cocreation and engaging communities from the beginning can improve immediate climate equity outcomes and enhance long-term stability of programmes by conveying relevant and culturally accessible climate information for socially and environmentally vulnerable groups, respecting existing cultural knowledge and values.</p> <p>Cities Mission Eol Info Toolkit (p64): A deliberative process involving citizens produces a set of well-informed recommendations that can form the basis of future policy decisions, rather than generating a list of top-of-mind opinions.</p> <p>100 Climate neutral Cities Mission (p13) "The Climate City Contract will therefore give citizens and civil society an active role and, as a pre-condition, will provide them with new platforms and better resources to design and implement climate actions."</p>
	Jury member	<p>Adaptation to Climate Change Implementation Plan (p8): promote inclusion and deliberative governance by developing citizen assemblies. (p42): Citizens Assemblies: to defining the mission within their community/city/region</p> <p>Cities Mission Eol Info Toolkit (p6): Expressions of Interest should describe their commitment to involve citizens and other stakeholders in planning and implementing their climate neutrality plans</p>
Citizen as user and consumer	Individual consumer or user with choice who compares and selects	Cities Mission Eol Info Toolkit (p34) Communication campaigns to improve the opinion of citizens on public transport reliability and safety
	Critical user, or consumer, group	<p>Cities Mission Eol Info Toolkit (p59) "Sidewalk Toronto" planned to be composed of climate-positive buildings. However, the project was criticised from the beginning by citizens who were concerned about how Alphabet would collect, protect, own and use their data. Block Sidewalk, a citizens' group, was particularly critical of the lack of transparency in the implementation of these smart city ideas and the fact that citizens were not adequately informed about how their data was being handled. In May 2020 it was announced that Sidewalk Labs would not be pursuing the Quayside project in Toronto.</p>
	Prosumers	<p>Cities Mission Eol Info Toolkit (p18) Mobilising prosumers (amongst other stakeholders) is an essential component of a sustained, durable and far-reaching effort for climate neutrality.</p> <p>Cities Mission Eol Info Toolkit (p83): "Some cities are supporting energy communities by joining and endorsing them, supporting the deployment of micro-grids, and taking advantage of vacant space in public buildings, such as solar roofs. Some Energia is a success story of a renewable energy cooperative in Spain, with more than 73 000 shareholders, including city agencies. The cooperative has multiple facilities producing more than 18,5 GWh per year that are commercialized through more than 130 000 contracts."</p>

The table above shows instances where 11 of the 13 roles were articulated in the Horizon Europe Mission reports that were studied.¹² It should be noted that, there was a great variance in how visible citizens were in each of the five mission areas. Moreover, whilst the diversity of citizen roles is somewhat visible in the aspirations of the Five European Missions, there was limited detail regarding how these citizen roles could be facilitated in the five missions.

The presence of 11 of the 13 citizen roles in the Mission Area reports and Mission Implementation reports for all five missions shows that the variety of distinct roles for citizens within the mission design and implementation is recognised and framed as integral to mission success. However, whilst there is indeed positioning of such roles as important, in the Mission reports at the time of writing there is little said about how each role can be supported and how each role can be best integrated into these five missions and when.

4. Reflections on mission-focused co-creation

What can we now say about the particular context of missions vis-à-vis co-creation? Are their new important requirements for co-creation as open innovation (see the MOSAIC definition of co-creation in section 3.6)?

For missions to be achieved, transformative change of whole socio-technical systems (mobility, healthcare, energy etc.) are needed. This will require technological and societal innovation as well as behavioural change. Moreover, the short-time horizon for the five missions of real impacts to be visible by 2030, requires that co-creation must lead to outcomes that can contribute to achieving the mission. **Thus, for mission-focused co-creation, there is a particular need for co-creation that is designed to lead to tangible outcomes (observable changes) that will contribute to mission success.**

The notion of contribution is important for missions. Without a clear picture of how the outcomes of co-creation processes will contribute to the mission, it is (a) unlikely that mission-focused co-creation processes will get the political support necessary and (b) unlikely to incentivise the variety of quadruple helix actors to participate in the first place (no clear outcomes, no point in participating). **Thus, for mission-oriented co-creation, it is necessary to clearly articulate the “mission contribution” of the co-creation outcomes.**

Missions are bold and ambitious, but also must be achievable and timebound. The five European missions require solutions to be found and major transformations to take place in the next eight years (by 2030). This requires (a) harnessing of as many innovative ideas as possible and (b) commitment of representatives of all quadruple helix co-creation partners to participate in the co-creation activity as well as ensure the legacy of the co-creation will lead to desirable impacts. This leads to two requirements for mission-focused co-creation. **Firstly, metrics for measuring the quality of co-creation processes is needed, to ensure all voices are heard and to maximise the chance of achieving innovative and relevant solutions for the mission. Secondly, anticipation of the legacy of co-creation,**

¹² It should be added that there was another category of citizen role visible in the Starfish mission – that of citizens providing solutions themselves through low tech, labour-intensive solutions. For example, in the Starfish Mission p18: “An increasing number of citizens engage in beach clean-up initiatives.” The Plastic Pirates initiative facilitates this 14th role of citizens.

the pathways from co-creation to mission contribution, must be an essential part of any co-creation activity that is focused on contributing to a mission.

Mariana Mazzucato (2019) emphasises that citizens are essential for designing, implementing, and evaluating missions. We have shown that this triple framing of citizens roles can be expanded to include a diversity of roles at different stages of the journey from mission design to mission contribution. Recognition that citizens can play a role in each stage of “innovation journeys” from concept to a solution impacting society is essential but understanding both the diversity of framings as well as tools and approaches to support appropriate and effective citizen involvement is key. However, for sustainable citizen involvement, as well as building trust and “buy in” from civil society more broadly, it is essential that citizens, and other quadruple helix actors involved in co-creation, are appropriately rewarded and that the rewards are fairly distributed across the different parties involved in co-creation. **Thus, it is essential that fair and equitable rewarding of participation in co-creation is an integral part of the design of co-creation activities and programmes.**

5. Conclusion

The objective of this deliverable was to get an understanding of what missions are, both in the context of Horizon Europe as well as more broadly. In addition, the deliverable aimed to capture how the roles that citizens have, or will play, have been framed in the five missions. With these insights, the deliverable, therefore, acts as a background and foundation paper that will be used to help guide the development, implementation and embedding of the MOSAIC co-creation approach.

This deliverable (Deliverable 3.1) will be mobilised to build MOSAIC co-creation design principles by cross-charting the insights from this report with the MOSAIC co-creation review (Deliverable 2.1). The results of the cross-charting exercise will be presented in Deliverable 3.2.

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